

Asteroid proper phase curves from Gaia photometry

Karri Muinonen^{1,2}, Antti Penttilä¹, Julia Grön¹, Alberto Cellino³, Xiaobin Wang⁴, Paolo Tanga⁵

¹ Department of Physics, University of Helsinki, Finland

² Finnish Geospatial Research Institute FGI, Masala, Finland

³ INAF, Osservatorio Astrofisico di Torino, Pino Torinese, Italy

⁴ Yunnan Observatories, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Kunming, China

⁵ Observatoire de la Cote d’Azur, Nice, France

Abstract

The photometric phase curve and lightcurve of an asteroid refer to the variation of the asteroid’s disk-integrated brightness as a function of the phase angle (the Sun-Object-Observer angle) and of time, respectively. They depend on the shape and rotation state of the asteroid, as well as the scattering properties of the asteroid’s surface. It follows that the shape, rotation state, and scattering properties can be estimated from the observations, to an extent allowed by the data available. We study the feasibility of retrieving phase curve parameters via statistical lightcurve inversion from the sparse asteroid photometry available from Gaia Data Release 2. With the help of the H, G_1, G_2 photometric function, we devise a surface reflection coefficient that gives rise to realistic disk-integrated phase curves. This allows us to derive phase curve parameters that are independent of the illumination and observation geometry. These proper phase curve parameters may allow for photometric classification of asteroids.

1 Introduction

Asteroids are nonspherical Solar System bodies typically rotating about their axes of maximum inertia. Their surfaces are assumed to be covered by regoliths, layers of particles in the size scales of microns to meters. Asteroids offer insight into the evolution of the Solar System. They provide valuable future space resources and cause a significant natural impact risk for the human kind.

Photometry is the most common source of data for the characterization of asteroid physical properties. The lightcurve, i.e., the observed brightness as a function of time, depends on the shape and spin state of the asteroid, as well as its scattering properties. We are developing statistical inverse methods for the retrieval of rotation periods, pole orientations, and scattering properties from the photometric observations. This entails a complete Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) assessment of the uncertainties in the physical parameters. The inverse methods are based on Lommel-Seeliger ellipsoids (LS ellipsoids) and convex shape models [1-4] suitable for the analyses of sparse data. The up-to-date inverse methods are available through a web-based Gaia Added Value Interface [5].

In the present work, we consider sparse photometric data from the ESA Gaia mission made available by Gaia Data Release 2 (Gaia DR2, [6]). Our focus is on asteroid (2867) Steins, which has played an important role in the scientific validation of Gaia DR2 data [6]. In Sect. 2, we describe the photometric modeling that gives rise to the definition of proper phase curves, phase curves that are independent of the asteroid’s orientation during the observations. Section 3 shows the validation of the Gaia DR2 data for Steins, followed by an assessment of the proper phase curve parameters of Steins using least squares fits and MCMC methods. Conclusions and future prospects close the article in Sect. 4.

Figure 1: Asteroid (2867) Steins [11, 12]. We show the north polar view (top left), south polar view (bottom left), the equatorial views at longitudes 0° (top middle) and 180° (top right), as well as the equatorial views at longitudes 90° (bottom middle) and 270° (bottom right).

2 Photometric model

Consider an asteroid in principal-axis rotation about its axis of maximum inertia, and denote its rotation period by P , pole orientation in ecliptic longitude and latitude by (λ, β) , and rotational phase at a given epoch t_0 by φ_0 .

The reflection coefficient R of a surface element on the asteroid relates the incident flux density πF_0 and the emergent intensity I as

$$I(\mu, \phi; \mu_0, \phi_0) = \mu_0 R(\mu, \phi; \mu_0, \phi_0) F_0, \quad (1)$$

$$\mu_0 = \cos \iota, \quad \mu = \cos \epsilon,$$

Table 1: The photometric G_1 and G_2 parameters for different asteroid taxonomic classes in the so-called single-parameter phase function by Penttilä et al. [9] based on the photometric observations reported by Shevchenko et al. [10].

Class	G_1	G_2
E	0.1505	0.6005
S/M	0.2588	0.3721
C	0.8228	0.0193
P	0.8343	0.0489
D	0.9617	0.0165

where ι and ϵ are the angles of incidence and emergence as measured from the outward normal vector of the element, and ϕ_0 and ϕ are the corresponding azimuthal angles. We measure ϕ so that the backscattering direction (or the direction of the Sun) is with $\phi = 0^\circ$. With the common assumption of a geometrically isotropic surface, specifying ϕ_0 is unnecessary.

The Lommel-Seeliger reflection coefficient (subscript LS) is (e.g., Wilkman et al. [7]),

$$R_{LS}(\mu, \mu_0, \phi) = \frac{1}{4} \tilde{\omega} P_{11}(\alpha) \frac{1}{\mu + \mu_0}, \quad (2)$$

where $\tilde{\omega}$ is the single-scattering albedo, P_{11} is the single-scattering phase function, and α is the phase angle, the angle between the Sun and the observer as seen from the object. The Lommel-Seeliger reflection coefficient, the first-order multiple-scattering approximation from the radiative transfer equation, is applicable to dark scattering media.

The disk-integrated brightness L equals the surface integral

$$\begin{aligned} L(\alpha) &= \int_{A_+} dA \mu I(\mu, \mu_0, \alpha) \\ &= \int_{A_+} dA \mu \mu_0 R(\mu, \mu_0, \alpha) F_0, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where A_+ specifies the part of the asteroid's surface that is both illuminated and visible. For a nonspherical asteroid, L can depend strongly on the orientation of the asteroid with respect to the scattering plane (the Sun-Object-Observer plane), where L is measured, giving rise to a lightcurve when the asteroid rotates.

For a spherical asteroid with diameter D , the disk-integrated brightness equals

$$\begin{aligned} L_0(\alpha) &= \frac{1}{32} \pi F_0 D^2 \tilde{\omega} P_{11}(\alpha) \Phi_0(\alpha), \\ \Phi_0(\alpha) &= 1 - \sin \frac{1}{2} \alpha \tan \frac{1}{2} \alpha \ln(\cot \frac{1}{4} \alpha), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where we have defined an auxiliary phase function $\Phi_0(\alpha)$ normalized to unity at zero phase angle.

Empirically, the disk-integrated brightness phase curve of an asteroid can be described by the H, G_1, G_2 phase function $\Phi_{HG_1G_2}$ (Muinonen et al. [8], Penttilä et al. [9], Shevchenko et al. [10]). We can link the empirical H, G_1, G_2 phase function with the physical reflection coefficient as follows. The geometric albedo p of a Lommel-Seeliger sphere is

$$p = \frac{1}{8} \tilde{\omega} P_{11}(0^\circ). \quad (5)$$

There are thus good reasons to expect that the model

$$\frac{1}{8} \tilde{\omega} P_{11}(\alpha) = p \frac{\Phi_{HG_1G_2}(\alpha)}{\Phi_0(\alpha)}, \quad (6)$$

that results in

$$R_{LS}(\mu, \mu_0, \phi) = 2p \frac{\Phi_{HG_1G_2}(\alpha)}{\Phi_0(\alpha)} \frac{1}{\mu + \mu_0}, \quad (7)$$

can work well in asteroid phase-curve analyses. The resulting disk-integrated brightness phase curves tend to mimic those observed for asteroids. For example, for a fictitious spherical asteroid, the phase curves now coincide with those described by the H, G_1, G_2 phase function.

It is important to note that the G_1, G_2 parameters in Eq. 7 refer to the multiple scattering properties of the surface element of an asteroid. They are thus different from the G_1, G_2 parameters derived from the direct fits of the H, G_1, G_2 phase function to the disk-integrated photometric data (e.g., [10]). In the present preliminary work, nevertheless, we do not yet introduce different mathematical symbols for the G_1, G_2 parameters in Eq. 7. However, we choose to term them the *proper* G_1, G_2 parameters.

Table 1 shows the G_1, G_2 parameters for the asteroid taxonomic classes E, S/M, C, P, and D as derived by Penttilä et al. [9]. Here the classes E and S/M constitute a photometric class of shallow phase curves, whereas the classes C, P, and D constitute a class of steep phase curves.

3 Results and discussion

The Gaia DR2 provides seven sparsely distributed photometric points for the E-class asteroid (2867) Steins (Fig. 2). In the literature [11,12], the rotation period is $P = 6.04681$ h and there are two possible pole orientations with the same period: $(\lambda, \beta) = (94^\circ, -85^\circ)$ (Pole 1) and $(\lambda, \beta) = (142^\circ, -83^\circ)$ (Pole 2). In what follows, we start by fixing $G_1 = 0.1505$ and $G_2 = 0.6005$ in agreement with Penttilä et al. [9].

We start with the Lommel-Seeliger (LS) ellipsoid inversion [1-3] by optimizing the rotational phase and the ellipsoid axial ratios b/a and c/a and keeping the remaining parameters fixed. For Pole 1, the least-squares fit is successful with an rms-value of 0.017 mag and with $\varphi_0 = 58^\circ$ ($t_0 = 51544.5$ MJD), $b/a = 0.83$, and $c/a = 0.46$. For Pole 2, the rms-value is minutely larger at 0.019 mag, with $\varphi_0 = 106^\circ$, $b/a = 0.83$, and $c/a = 0.40$. Based on the LS-ellipsoid analysis, Pole 1 emerges as a favored solution due to the more spherical shape and better rms-value.

Let us next incorporate the high-resolution shape model of Steins available from a shape analysis based on the disk-resolved imaging during the Rosetta mission flyby and disk-integrated ground-based lightcurve observations [11,12] (Fig. 1). With the aforescribed parameter values but varying the rotational phase systematically with 0.1-degree resolution over its full range of $[0^\circ, 360^\circ]$, we compute the rms-value between the Gaia data and the disk-integrated brightness from the high-resolution model. For Pole 1, we obtain the minimum rms-value of 0.026 mag at $\varphi_0 = 244.2^\circ$ and, for Pole 2, the rms is 0.020 mag at $\varphi_0 = 282.8^\circ$. Thus, based on the high-resolution shape model, Pole 2 is preferred. Note that the apparent orientation of the asteroid in space, at any epoch, is approximately the same for the best-fit solutions corresponding to Poles 1 and 2. Figure 2 shows the Gaia

Figure 2: Photometry of asteroid (2867) Steins from Gaia DR2 (red circles) validated for Poles 1 (left) and 2 (right; see text) using a high-resolution shape model (blue crosses, [11,12]) with a Lommel-Seeliger scattering law and E-class G_1, G_2 phase curve parameters (Table 1).

DR2 photometric points together with the present, computed results using Poles 1 and 2. Although the photometric data set is scarce, one may argue that the distribution of residuals is more balanced in the case of Pole 2.

It is reasonable to study the feasibility of obtaining phase curve parameters for Steins with the help of the high-resolution model. We can start with the average G_1, G_2 parameters (Table 1). Using Pole 2, for the E-class parameters $G_1 = 0.1505$ and $G_2 = 0.6005$ and S-class parameters $G_1 = 0.2588$ and $G_2 = 0.3721$, the best rms-value continues to be low at 0.020 mag. However, for the C-class parameters $G_1 = 0.8228$ and $G_2 = 0.0193$, the rms-value deteriorates significantly and obtains the value of 0.030 mag. Thus, the Gaia DR2 photometric points together with the high-resolution shape model suggest that Steins is an object with a shallow phase curve, presumably a high-albedo or moderate-albedo object, that is, *not* a low-albedo object.

The present analysis indicates, first, that the photometric data from Gaia DR2 can have a precision better than 0.02 mag. Second, it will be challenging to obtain better fits by assuming homogeneous scattering properties, that is, the same scattering model, across the entire surface of Steins. Third, the good fits validate the software developed for the LS-ellipsoid. Fourth, successful ray tracing for the high-resolution shape model with concavities validate the ray-tracing part of the inversion software. We would like to point out that a large part of the rms difference is likely to derive from the modeling and that the Gaia data can have significantly smaller uncertainties.

In Fig. 3, we show the MCMC inversion with 2000 pairs of G_1, G_2 values for the proper phase curve parameters of Steins using the Gaia DR2 data and the high-resolution shape model of Steins. For Pole 1, we obtain the mean values and their $1-\sigma$ uncertainties $G_1 = 0.26 \pm 0.18$ and $G_2 = 0.41 \pm 0.15$. The correlation coefficient is $\text{Cor}(G_1, G_2) = -0.34$. For Pole 2, the corresponding values are $G_1 = 0.25 \pm 0.17$, $G_2 = 0.46 \pm 0.14$, and $\text{Cor}(G_1, G_2) = -0.41$. The mean values are strikingly close to the S-class mean values (Table 1). However, the uncertainties allow for both E-class and S-

class phase curves. Furthermore, we recall that the proper G_1, G_2 values can differ from the mean values in Table 1 obtained by direct H, G_1, G_2 fits to photometric data.

4 Conclusion

We conclude that the present inverse methods can facilitate a meaningful retrieval of proper asteroid phase curves from sparse Gaia DR2 photometry. The retrieval can lead to photometric classification of asteroids based on the steepness of their phase curves. We point out that the interrelation between an asteroid's taxonomic class (see Table 1) and its phase curve can be complex.

Based on a preliminary study without a priori information about the shape and rotation state, the Gaia DR2 data can allow us to derive photometric classes (shallow or steep phase curves) for asteroids with more than 15 observations, that is, for more than 2100 asteroids.

Acknowledgments

Research supported, in part, by the Academy of Finland Grant No. 1298137 and by the ERC Advanced Grant No 320773 (SAEMPL). This work presents results from the European Space Agency (ESA) space mission Gaia. Gaia data are being processed by the Gaia Data Processing and Analysis Consortium (DPAC).

References

- [1] Muinonen, K., and Lumme, K. Disk-integrated brightness of a Lommel-Seeliger scattering ellipsoidal asteroid. *Astron. Astrophys.* 584, A23, 2015.
- [2] Cellino, A., Muinonen, K., Hestroffer, D., and Carbognani, A.: Inversion of sparse photometric data of asteroids using triaxial ellipsoid shape models and a Lommel-Seeliger scattering law. *Planet. Space Sci.*, 118, pp. 221-226, 2015.
- [3] Muinonen, K., Wilkman, O., Cellino, A., Wang, X., and Wang, Y.: Asteroid lightcurve inversion with Lommel-Seeliger ellipsoids. *Planet. Space Sci.*, 118, pp. 227-241, 2015.

Figure 3: Markov-chain Monte Carlo inversion for the proper phase curve parameters of asteroid (2867) Steins in the case of Pole 1 (left) and 2 (right) using seven photometric observations from Gaia DR2 [6] and the high-resolution shape model powered by the Rosetta mission [11,12]. See Table 2 and text for further information. The results suggest that (2867) Steins does *not* belong to the class of asteroids with steep photometric phase curves.

[4] Muinonen, K., Torppa, J., Wang, X., Cellino, A. Asteroid lightcurve inversion with Bayesian inference. *Astron. Astrophys.*, in preparation, 2019.

[5] Torppa, J., Granvik, M., Penttilä, A., Reitmaa, J. Tudosse, V., Peltari, L., Muinonen, K., Bakker, J., Navarro, V., O’Mullane, W. Added-value interfaces to asteroid photometric and spectroscopic data in the Gaia database. *Adv. Space Res.* 62, pp. 464-476, 2018.

[6] Gaia Collaboration, Spoto, F., et al. Gaia Data Release 2: Observations of solar system objects. *Astron. Astrophys.* 616, A13, 2018.

[7] Wilkman, O., Muinonen, K., and Peltoniemi, J. Photometry of dark atmosphereless planetary bodies: an efficient numerical model. *Planet. Space Sci.* 118, pp. 250-255, 2015.

[8] Muinonen, K., Belskaya, I. N., Cellino, A., Delbò, M., Lvasseur-Regourd, A.-C., Penttilä, A., and Tedesco, E. F. A three-parameter magnitude phase function for asteroids. *Icarus* 209, pp. 542-555, 2010.

[9] Penttilä, A., Muinonen, K., Shevchenko, V. G., and Wilkman, O. H. G1, G2 photometric phase function extended to low-accuracy data. *Planet. Space Sci.* 123, pp. 117-125, 2016.

[10] Shevchenko, V. G., Belskaya, I. N., Muinonen, K., Penttilä, A., Krugly, Y. N., Velichko, F. P., Chiorny, V. G., Slyusarev, I. C., Gaftonyuk, N. M., and Tereschenko, I. A. Asteroid observations at low phase angles. IV. Average parameters for the new H, G1, G2 magnitude system. *Planet. Space Sci.* 123, pp. 101-116, 2016.

[11] Jorda, L., Lamy, P. L., Gaskell, R. W., Kaasalainen, M., Groussin, O., Besse, S., Faury, G. Asteroid (2867) Steins: Shape, topography and global physical properties from OSIRIS observations. *Icarus* 221, pp. 1089-1100, 2012.

[12] Farnham, T. L., Jorda, L., RO-A-OSINAC/OSIWAC-5-STEINS-SHAPE-V1.0, NASA Planetary Data System, 2013.